

STRYCHNINE AND BRUCINE. PART I. THE ALKALINE DEGRADATION OF STRYCHNINE.

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Distillation of strychnine with potassium hydroxide gives among the products a base (picrate, m.p. 142°), which is identical with the base A described by Clemo.

Goldschmidt (*Ber.*, 1882, 18, 1977) obtained indole and an oil which he called γ -picoline by fusing strychnine with caustic potash. Stöhr (*Ber.*, 1887, 20, 810, 1808) obtained scatole, β -picoline, and ethylpyridine as degradation products but Mofatti and Löbisch obtained β -picoline, carbazole and scatole (*Monatsh.*, 1888, 9, 626) under similar conditions. Clemo, Perkin and Robinson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 1589) isolated indole, carbazole and a picrate of a base which melted at 168°. Kotake (*Proc. Acad. Tokyo*, 1936, 12, 4, 99) announced the important discovery of the formation of 3-indolyethylamine by fusion of strychninolone, strychninonic acid or even strychnine with potassium hydroxide. After this announcement Clemo (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 1695) reported the isolation of basic and non-basic products by fusing strychnine with potassium hydroxide under very mild conditions. Among the non-basic products, he identified indole and 3-ethylindole. Two of the three basic products which he isolated remained unidentified and the third in all probability seemed to be tryptamine, but on account of the conflicting data in the literature, the final recognition of the substance was temporarily held up.

The present work was started in November, 1935 but owing to the publication of the above papers it was discontinued. However, along with other products one base was isolated which seemed to be common both to strychnine and brucine and different from that obtained by Kotake. This was purified through its picrate and subsequently by fractional distillation; the picrate (m.p. 141-42°) appeared from its melting point and analytical data to be the picrate of 2-methyl-4-ethylpyridine. 2-Methyl-4-ethylpyridine was synthesised by Hantzsch's method but its picrate (m.p. 142°) depressed the m.p. of the picrate of the strychnine degradation base and melted at 115-125°. Thus it showed conclusively that it was not 2-methyl-4-ethylpyridine but some other isomer of it. Clemo reports that the m.p. and the mixed m.p. of the picrate of his base and the foregoing picrate to be 143-44° (*private communication*), thus establishing the identity of the two.

The author obtained the base under drastic conditions by distilling the intimate mixture of strychnine and potassium hydroxide in a copper flask,

while Clemo carried out his experiment under very mild conditions. Credit must be given to Clemo and Kotake, who independently isolated β -3-indolyethylamine and this observation justifies the consistent contention of Robinson that strychnine and brucine are hydroindole derivatives in which the positions 2 and 3 (α - and β -) are thrice substituted (*cf. J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 941) and carry but a single hydrogen atom. This observation was interpreted by a slightly modified formula (I) for strychnine by the author as suggested by Robinson (*cf. Oxford University Thesis for D.Phil.*, 1937) but Holmes and Robinson's re-examination of the action of bromine on diketonucidine is an important contribution on the subject and now the balance of evidence is in favour of formula (II) (*cf. J. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 603).

EXPERIMENTAL

Fusion of Strychnine with Caustic Potash (*cf. Abstracts of Dissertations*, Oxford, 1938, 173).

Strychnine (1 part) was intimately mixed with powdered potassium hydroxide (3 parts) and water (1 part) and the paste distilled from a copper flask heated by a gradually strengthened free flame. Water and a straw coloured oil with a strong odour distilled over. The distillate was extracted with ether and the ethereal solution was shaken with 10% hydrochloric acid. The ether extract, after washing with sodium hydroxide solution and water, was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and on removal of solvent gave an oily neutral product with a strong odour. This was not investigated further.

The acid extract was made alkaline with sodium hydroxide and was shaken with ether four times. The ethereal solution was washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The addition of picric acid in ether to the dried ethereal solution precipitated a bright yellow picrate which was well washed with ether. The filtrate and washings on standing

gave another bright yellow picrate, m.p. 186-87°. After two crystallisations from methyl alcohol it had m.p. 195-96°. (Found in material dried at 100° in *vacuo*: C, 63.6; H, 4.1; N, 16.8 per cent). The picrate was insufficient for further characterisation.

The main bright yellow picrate was decomposed with sodium hydroxide solution and water and then shaken four times with ether. The ethereal extract was washed with water and dried over solid potassium hydroxide. On removal of the solvent, an oily straw-coloured liquid remained which was fractionally distilled. The lower boiling fraction was converted into its picrate and after crystallisation from alcohol several times was obtained in large bright yellow leaflets, m. p. 141-42°. (Clemo found the m.p. and the mixed m.p. with the picrate of his base "A" to be 143-44°). It is soluble in alcohol, acetone, chloroform, benzene and ethyl acetate, and insoluble in ether and petroleum ether. [Found in material dried at 100° in *vacuo*: C, 48.0, 47.9; H, 4.3, 4.0; N, 15.2, 15.3. $C_8H_{11}N^+C_6H_2(NO_2)_3(OH)$ requires C, 48.0; H, 4.0; N, 16.0 per cent].

The micro-analyses were done by Dr. Weiller and Dr. Strauss, Oxford.

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